

AIAL's Comments for the Consultation on Digital Omnibus (Digital Package on Simplification)

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ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets. We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

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Executive Summary

We welcome the Commission's proposals on simplifying the regulations. However, we consider several aspects as being problematic, and therefore do not recommend accepting them at this stage. We summarise our views as follows:

1. **Definition of Personal Data: should be rejected** as it drastically changes the scope of the GDPR, affects its rights, and has a material impact on the fundamental right to data protection as defined in Article 8 of CFR.
2. **Facilitating use of personal data in AI systems: approach with caution** as it introduces unwanted 'side-effects' and risks GDPR's 'neutrality'.
3. **Restriction of GDPR rights: should be rejected** as they are disproportionate, the solutions are not likely to be effective, and they have an impact on fundamental rights which have been enabled through the use of the GDPR rights.
4. **Harmonisation of DPIA Requirements: should be accepted with changes** regarding ensuring the competency of EDPB as the authority rather than the Commission as outlined in the document.
5. **Privacy Signals: should be accepted with changes** related to the scope, validity, and introduction of considerations to ensure this does not create unwanted effects such as further popups or dark patterns. *This is a detailed section with considerations on existing privacy signals, addressing consent fatigue, a gap analysis of Article 88b provisions, addressing the issue of automating 'given consent', and suggesting criteria for defining validity of privacy signals.*

The 'Digital Omnibus' series of legislative proposals include key changes to the GDPR, one of which is addressing the issues surrounding 'consent fatigue' and strengthening users' privacy rights online'.¹ This document is the feedback submitted to the public consultation

¹ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL amending Regulations (EU) 2016/679, (EU) 2018/1724, (EU) 2018/1725, (EU) 2023/2854 and Directives 2002/58/EC, (EU) 2022/2555 and (EU) 2022/2557 as regards the simplification of the digital legislative framework, and repealing Regulations (EU) 2018/1807, (EU) 2019/1150, (EU) 2022/868, and Directive (EU) 2019/1024 (Digital Omnibus) COM/2025/837 final

associated with this proposal.² The document provides a holistic overview of the problem space regarding 'consent' and 'privacy management', describes the ecosystem, its actors, and their behaviours that have led to the problem, analyses the current state of technical solutions and their standardisation status, and to identify concrete recommendations to the proposed GDPR Article 88b to ensure materialisation of the intended benefits.

Rejection of Redefining Personal Data

The Commission's rationale in the introduction of the omnibus mechanism and the accompanying proposal for amending the GDPR is that these are mere 'technical changes' and therefore no impact assessments are necessary. However, the changes include a new definition for personal data (Article 4(1) and Article 41a), which is in effect a reduction of the concept by considering certain forms of '(pseudo-)anonymity' as not being personal data. This clearly cannot be a technical change as the scope of the GDPR is firmly decided based on the processing of personal data. Ergo, any change to the definition of this concept also changes the entire regulation and its applicability, and therefore impacts all its intended objectives – including the enforcement of Article 8 of the Charter on Fundamental Rights regarding data protection as well as the rights introduced in the regulation itself.

Further to this, the revised definition considers a 'subjective' criteria where the definition is to be determined by the controller without any further qualifiers, and where the new definition precludes the data subject from understanding when a controller has misinterpreted themselves as not being within the scope of the GDPR due to it. It also severely affects the ability of supervisory authorities to understand the processing activities, and introduces a new test – for both controllers and authorities – to determine whether data is indeed personal and what is its applicability under the GDPR. This risks complexity rather than the intended simplification.

The rationale for this change is given as a formal encoding of the CJEU case law³, however, it is important to note that the case law in question is 1) not absolute in nature; 2) did not reinterpret the definition of personal data but stressed the need for a case-by-case application; and 3) asked the lower court to apply its *frame opinion* to the case. There are several other CJEU case laws⁴ which have been *complete* in their judgements and application, and which counter the proposed definition. We also note that the EDPB and EDPS in their joint opinion⁵ also share a similar reasoning and therefore also indicate that this should not be accepted.

We therefore request that this provision on changing the definition of personal data be rejected, and that due procedure be followed in terms of the proposed Digital Fitness Check where this can be better explored along with the use of the impact assessment as stated in the Better Regulation toolkit.

² Call for Evidence: Digital Omnibus Ref. Ares(2025)7724296 - 16/09/2025

³ C-413/23P EDPS v SRB

⁴ C-604/22 IAB Europe, C-582/14 Breyer, and C-683/21 Nacionalinis visuomenes sveikatos centra

⁵ Digital Omnibus: EDPB and EDPS support simplification and competitiveness while raising key concerns https://www.edpb.europa.eu/news/news/2026/digital-omnibus-edpb-and-edps-support-simplification-and-competitiveness-while_en

Caution against Processing in AI Systems

The proposal introduces several targeted mechanisms (GDPR Article 9(2)(k), Article 9(5), Article 88c; AI Act Article 4a) through which the use of personal data is facilitated specifically and exclusively for the development and use of AI models and systems. While we agree with the need for clarity and a stimulating interpretation that permits rapid innovation in the field of AI, we do not agree with the current approach of doing so at the risk of fundamental changes to the GDPR, and the weakening of data subject rights and freedoms.

First, the GDPR was developed to be a technologically neutral regulation. By creating specific provisions for the use of personal data risks disrupting this by allowing uses of personal data for AI, where the same uses would not be allowed for any other technology. The principle of data protection laws has consistently been to foresee the necessity to address technologies yet to be developed, and therefore the existing provisions of GDPR are not 'ignorant' of the AI, but rather are intended to be applied regardless of it. It should therefore be a question of how to align the rights and requirements of the GDPR rather than to bypass them altogether – as doing so is disproportionate to the data subject even if it may be beneficial to the commercial interests and in some limited cases – public interests.¹

Second, currently the AI companies that stand to benefit from these provisions do not practice sufficient transparency or demonstrate any practices that assure they will respect the intended changes in line with the principles being assumed. For example, our research⁶ has shown that the public summaries of training content required under the AI Act's Article 53(1)(d) are not being provided despite it being over a year since we have had the Act's final text, and 6 months since the obligation became applicable. This public summary contains a section on the involvement of personal data, both from direct (e.g. service use) and indirect (e.g. crawled or obtained from third parties), and which directly relates to GDPR Articles 13 and 14. We found only 4 summaries till date, and all are small providers or open-source initiatives, and no summaries from any of the big AI providers. The typical reasons for this are claims of confidentiality, IP, copyright, business secrets, amongst others, even though the GDPR already requires this information to be provided as part of the applicable rights.

Third, the proposed changes will fundamentally change the nature of EU law, which has always upheld the data subject's fundamental rights to privacy and data protection as part of their ability to self-determine their life and actions, including within digital spheres. By implementing the proposal, it risks creating a system whereby data subjects must individually manage their personal data for each company – as the system would now be to 'opt-out' by objecting to legitimate interests. In most cases, the data subjects would not even know which company has collected data and from where, and where it is being used. In the same vein, most companies would also not have the contact details of data subjects, and thus not be able to inform them about the objections. The proposal also does not state how such objections would work – what would be a reasonable time frame to wait for data subjects to 'discover' the proposed training and thus object? Further, objections to legitimate interests are a right, and cannot be bound to a specific time limit. The GDPR envisions no

⁶ Blankvoort, D. A. H., Pandit, H. J., & Gahntz, M. (2026). Quality Assessment of Public Summary of Training Content for GPAI models required by AI Act Article 53(1)(d) (preprint). 9th ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT), Montreal, Canada. Zenodo. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18803975 <https://aial.ie/research/gpai-training-transparency/>

system whereby the data subject is prevented from exercising a right just because a specific period of time has lapsed. AI models, once trained, cannot be modified in a way that the data subject's personal data can be selectively removed. **We therefore request that the provisions enabling indiscriminate use of personal data for AI be removed, and as part of the Digital Fitness Check a proportionate set of solutions be identified.**

Rejection of Rights Restriction

The proposal asks that existing rights in the GDPR be limited in their scope, in the ability of the data subject to exercise them, and in some cases to be removed entirely. The accompanying staff working document does not provide clear details on how these choices were decided upon, as there are subjective arguments without considerations to the data subject's reduced ability to have transparency – which is directly associated with not only their fundamental right to data protection as defined in Article 8 of the CFR, but also the right to privacy as defined in Article 7. Therefore, **it is important that any changes made to the right do not disturb the existing legal mechanisms without a sufficient impact assessment, as well as a study on whether these measures: 1) are proportionate to the actuality of the problems for both controllers and data subjects; 2) are the best and least destructive of the alternative identified; and 3) that they will actually simplify things. In its current stage, neither of the three are likely to be achieved.**

In particular:

- Article 12(5) has existing language to prevent 'abuse' that is sufficient, and the proposal is disproportionate in that it only considers potentially marginal cases when most of the information is already required to be provided under Article 13 and 14 to the data subject. The EDPB and EDPS opinion already confirms this as such.
- Article 13(4) being limited risks also affecting other rights which rely on having access to information, and thereby to exercise other rights – not only in GDPR but also in other spheres of law, society, and private life.
- Article 13(5) is in direct conflict with established practices, such as where research institutes have long practiced codes for research integrity, including its consolidation as an 'European code of conduct'. The exception also allows data subjects to 'lose' their data to service providers who may use it for any 'research' activities – including training of AI models under the provided justification.
- Article 22 in the current text of the GDPR explicitly provides a right to the data subject to object to the use of automated decision making. The proposal changes the phrasing such that even if the meaning may seem to be intact, the 'right of the data subject' has been replaced with an 'obligation of the controller'. This is problematic as it should be clear that a 'right' has a special meaning and interpretation in law. This also allows the controller to be the decisive entity rather than the data subject, which is clearly not the intent of the provision in GDPR. Further, the change also concerns replacing a 'prohibition' with a 'permission' which also have distinct meaning and interpretation in law – especially considering the material effect of not allowing unless conditions are met (prohibitive) as opposed to allowing by meeting conditions (permissive). This phrasing is also used deliberately in Article 9(1) to have a similar effect, and should thus be retained in Article 22(1).

Improvements to Data Breach Notifications

We appreciate the effort to simplify the obligations related to data breach notifications. We also welcome the requirement for the EDPB to provide a common template for this obligation, and which would contain a list of circumstances where the breach should be considered high-risk and thus trigger further obligations. However, we have several concerns regarding the provision as it is currently being proposed:

1. What is meant by 'high-risk' is not clearly defined in the GDPR, and is thus left to the subjective interpretations of the actors in question. Currently, authorities rely on the preliminary information being provided to understand when breaches become high-risk, and therefore they are in a position to follow through on the following obligations. By requiring the controllers to determine when a breach is high-risk, it is now a question of whether a controller can 'hide' breaches – and if so then how can authorities and data subjects become aware of this.
2. The preparation of the template should not be at the discretion of the Commission as the GDPR does not consider the Commission a competent supervisory authority for the purposes of the GDPR. Further, the Commission also has neither an office nor a team set up to manage GDPR, and is therefore unlikely to be aware of evolving situations and trends. Current supervisory authorities already have the competency as well as existing lists and considerations that require consolidation through EDPB into an EU-wide criteria. This should be continued, and done so alongside other EDPB activities such as guidelines, codes of conduct, and certifications. The Commission can independently decide to consolidate those criteria which are considered 'stable' into an implementing act while the EDPB remains responsible for managing the evolving situation and maintaining a dynamic list.
3. To reduce burdens and achieve simplicity, the provision should be changed for the EDPB to also consider a 'whitelist' or 'low risk' breaches which do not require expensive notifications and operations based on an assessment of factors (scale, sensitivity, etc.). Such aspects are already part of several data breach notification forms found on authority websites.

Harmonisation of Data Protection Impact Assessments

We welcome this provision as this would create a single EU-wide criteria for what is considered 'high-risk' under the GDPR (and requires a DPIA) and what is considered 'not high-risk' under the GDPR (and does not require a DPIA). In our past research,⁷ we have already analysed and compared DPIA required lists from each GDPR supervisory authority, which shows the current extent of overlaps and divergences. Going further, we have also compared these with the high-risk criteria in the AI Act (Annex III) to understand the interplay between the GDPR and the AI Act. Currently we are performing a similar exercise for the DPIA not required lists with the same objectives.

As with the template for the data breach notifications outlining which criteria are high-risk, and the Commission's determining role in deciding these, we consider that these DPIA required and not-required lists are best conducted by the EDPB due to its competence in

⁷ Rintamäki, T., Golpayegani, D., Lewis, D., Celeste, E., & Pandit, H. J. (2026, February 26). Impact Assessment Requirements in the GDPR vs the AI Act: Overlaps, Divergence, and Implications. Retrieved from osf.io/6qhzj

relation to the GDPR as well as experience of working with them beyond making lists e.g. by providing guidelines on DPIA, approving codes of conduct and certifications which relate to risk assessment measures, and so on.

We request the Commission to provide an implementing act for better aligning the requirements for the GDPR with those in the AI Act in relation to risk and impact assessments where the EDPB-provided lists can be better utilised for the AI Act and vice-versa. For this, we note that the Article 27 of the AI Act already refers to the AI Act and requires a 'tool' to be provided by the Commission – which is yet to be announced. We request that such a tool benefit from this alignment between the GDPR and the AI Act. For this, we have prior research that suggests considerations.⁸

Implementing Privacy Managers Under GDPR's Article 88b

Understanding 'consent' as a technical process

Box 1 The technical implementation of consent has the following components, not all of which may be implemented in the same solution or be designed, developed, or provided by the same 'vendor', or be made available to the controller or data subject:

1. Technical means for the controller to express information on intended processing, and on the basis of which they are requesting the data subject's consent.⁹
2. Technical means for the controller to issue a notice and request to provide information to the data subject with the goal of obtaining their consent.¹⁰
3. Technical means for the data subject to express their decision while meeting the requirements of the GDPR regarding the validity of the decision.¹¹
4. Technical means to communicate the decision back to the controller.¹²
5. Technical means for the data subject to withdraw their consent.¹³
6. Technical means to communicate the withdrawal back to the controller.¹⁴

'Consent' is a generic legal principle for an able individual to assent or agree to some *action*. It is also a social concept that implies an acceptance of *things* and has a broader remit than legal enforceability or requirements.¹⁵ In the GDPR, it is also one of the legal bases that

⁸ Rintamaki, T., & Pandit, H. J. (2024). Towards An Automated AI Act FRIA Tool That Can Reuse GDPR's DPIA. arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.14756. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.14756>

⁹ The IAB's TCF framework is an example of a de-facto industry 'standard' for this

¹⁰ The implementations by CMPs that show pop-ups are an example of generating the notice

¹¹ This can be a button, a tick box, or other user-interface means.

¹² The CMP's implementation and the RTB mechanism are examples of such communication.

¹³ Websites allowing data subjects to revisit the same consent dialogue where they made their initial decision is an example of the 'as easy' requirement. While the GDPR only requires withdrawal to be made available, controllers may also allow the same interface to re-confirm or refresh consent i.e. confirm the data subject still agrees with given consent.

¹⁴ Notably, the IAB's TCF and RTB mechanisms do not support this requirement fully.

¹⁵ For example of broader implications of consent, see the seminal work "Manufacturing Consent: The Political Economy of the Mass Media" by Edward S. Herman and Noam Chomsky (1988) and "Consentability: Consent and Its Limits" by Nancy S. Kim (2019)

justifies how personal data could be processed.¹⁶ In this context, consent is the action expressed by the individual that determines the processing of their personal data, and whose validity is determined based on meeting the requirements stipulated by GDPR and its implementations (guidance, case law, and so on). The GDPR puts the onus on the controllers to ensure that the data subject's consent is valid and that it is demonstrable.¹⁷ For technical solutions to support this process, we first require an explicit elaboration of the process by which consenting happens. I describe it as follows:

1. The service provider (as a controller) determines the need for some processing of personal data to be carried out, and also determines that this requires obtaining the data subject's consent.
2. The information obtained in step 1 allows the controller to describe their intended processing activity in order to obtain informed consent from the data subject. Typically, this is done via a 'notice', such as that shown in the 'cookie pop-ups' and 'consent dialogues' on websites.¹⁸ It can also be done as part of other existing processes, for example in settings or dashboards, or as part of forms. The notice can be short and concise if the data subject already has all sufficient information, or it can be long and complex if the data subject is to be informed about several things.¹⁹
3. The data subject is presented with the information and asked to make a decision. This decision can be: accept the proposed processing and 'give consent', or to not accept it and 'refuse consent'. The data subject may also have the ability to delay making a decision and 'not make a decision' – for example by closing the dialogue or not clicking a button straight away. Practicality may necessitate multiple decisions to be requested at the same time, making the interface and process more complex.²⁰
4. The decision is communicated to the controller who then must record it or be in a position to demonstrate that the decision was made – especially when it is the data subject giving consent as this is the legal basis for the processing of personal data.
5. The controller then must also make available the means for the data subject to change their decision, at minimal the ability to withdraw their given consent, which is declared as a right of the data subject under the GDPR.²¹ This is necessary to be done via the same interface or equivalent means in order to meet the GDPR's requirements for withdrawal being as easy as giving consent.²²

From the controller's perspective, the obligations are to request the consent in a valid manner, which the GDPR also states as requiring specific forms of actions from the data subject, ensuring there are no conflicting conditions that cast a doubt on the principle of 'free will', and that the data subject is cognisant of their decision and its implications. Legally, these are referred to under the terms 'freely given', 'specific', and 'informed' in the GDPR.

¹⁶ Article 6(1)(a) GDPR

¹⁷ Article 7(1) GDPR

¹⁸ Henceforth the article only uses 'consent dialogues' as 'cookie pop-ups' imply a restricted set of consent only about the use of cookies whereas the remit of GDPR and the nuisance of online pop-ups goes much beyond these. The author believes that framing the narrative on this is essential to appropriately address the core issues of consent fatigue and resilience to solutions.

¹⁹ In particular, the obligation to provide information is specified in Articles 13 and 14 GDPR

²⁰ In particular, consent dialogues used on websites request multiple consent instances as well as implementing the obligation to inform the data subject about the use of legitimate interests and the ability to object to it pursuant to Article 21(1). This is despite Article 7(2) requiring consent requests to be presented "in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from other matters".

²¹ Article 7(4) GDPR

²² *id.* (*idem* or *'id'* is latin, and is used to mean same citation as previous reference)

These have established meanings²³ and tests for validity which reduce subjectivity even if investigations might require a case-by-case approach. However, these meanings and interpretations are not absolute and are required to be revised based on the evolution of technologies – in particular regarding devices, interfaces, and the context of what processing of personal data is being dictated by the consent decision. This includes the potential for automation of certain actions and parts of the technical implementation.²⁴

Data subject's perspective on 'online privacy'

Box 2 The technical implementation of a data subject's expectation of online privacy translates into generic principles – with consent as 'opt-in' meaning the data subject must first agree to start processing, and legitimate interests as 'opt-outs' meaning the data subject is not required to agree but to disagree to stop processing. Other legal bases may have variations of these, but these are not discussed here. The notion of online privacy can thus be described as technical implementations for the data subject that allows:

1. Understanding whether processing requires opt-ins or opt-outs
2. For opt-ins, expressing a decision (agree, disagree)
3. For opt-outs, expressing a decision (permit, object)
4. For any decision, change a decision made previously

In orthogonal to these factors, a data subject's perception is also shaped by expectations of technical capabilities from the devices and software that they use and which should work in their favour and assist them in enforcing their privacy expectations.²⁵

The GDPR is a law implementing the fundamental right to data protection which requires all processing of personal data to be based on consent or another legal basis.²⁶ However, it also aligns with the fundamental right to privacy, both in the forms expressed in the Charter²⁷ as well as how the concept of privacy is understood socially. In this sense, the GDPR's prescription of consent as a legal basis is not seen as a separate mechanism, but as a part of a larger set of options that allow data subjects to understand, control, and direct their 'online privacy'. Data subjects are unlikely to be GDPR experts and thus cannot appreciate the nuances of the different legal basis (consent and legitimate interests in particular) and how this translates into specific rights (withdrawal for consent and objection for legitimate interests), or what should be the correct implementation of these in a given situation. Despite Article 8 of the Charter allowing for diversity of legal bases, the data subject's perception of their private life thus extends to their 'online privacy', which translates into an expectation that they be allowed to use 'consent' as a way to control (or avoid) as many activities as possible. This is also referred to as the principle of self-determination.²⁸

²³ EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679 Version 1.1 (2020)

²⁴ Florea, M., & Esteves, B. (2023). Is automated consent in solid GDPR-compliant? an approach for obtaining valid consent with the solid protocol. *Information*, 14(12), 631.

²⁵ W3C Statement – Privacy Principles (2025)

²⁶ Article 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights (2000)

²⁷ Article 7 Charter of Fundamental Rights (2000)

²⁸ id 18 – (means see previous footnote – in this case 18)

Consent Fatigue: An emergent symptom of underlying problems

- Box 3** The challenges associated with consent and online privacy can be summarised as:
1. Over time, solutions made available for data subjects have been reduced in features by only allowing users minimal choice to "object" and to "opt-out" based on narratives regarding privacy risks from fingerprinting potential, complexity of implementation, or ease of adoption.
 2. There are inherent conflicts of interest in the implementation by actors involved in the IAB TCF and RTB ecosystems, including large platforms and CMPs, who have a vested interest in malcompliance and who develop ways to subvert or violate requirements as not doing so would result in economic disadvantages to them despite massive privacy impacts to individuals. These include use of dark patterns, developing specifications that do not fully align with legal principles or requirements, and abusing their role in the ecosystem to subvert compliance at scale. It is vital to consider these acts through the lens of recidivism and assume these actors are unlikely to change their behaviour or to act in good faith.
 3. The online experience is predominantly shaped by specific actors who control the device, OS, and software (in particular web browsers), and who exert this power to gatekeep what privacy and data protection should mean. So far, they have not shown the will to design or implement technical solutions in a way that is aligned with the EU's laws or principles, and they may continue to not do so – especially as several actors also overlap with those identified in Point 2.
 4. The technical solutions, often sponsored by or involving members of actors highlighted in Points 1 and 2, have not been aligned with the reality of experiences faced by individuals, in particular to address cookie/consent popups and fatigue. Where solutions have been proposed, they are predominantly US-centric, work in ways contrary to exercising of fundamental rights, and are intentionally designed to be non-aligned with legal enforceability. These create barriers and increase the efforts needed for determining and enforcing compliance.

The primary reason consent is an issue and is being addressed in the Omnibus proposal is 'consent fatigue' – a term used to refer to the excessive consent decisions that data subjects have to make repeatedly across devices, websites, and platforms. Because the data subjects are shown popups immediately on first visit, it also stops them from accessing the website or service, and creates an impression that consent itself is the problem.²⁹ However, this is not true – neither the GDPR nor any other law requires these popups or to frustrate the users. The problem of consent fatigue is widespread because the underlying mechanisms and implementations are uniform and part of the same implementation practices – the IAB's TCF mechanism which enables the Real-Time Bidding (RTB) online advertising, as well as because the CMPs implementing it do so in ways that violate key

²⁹ Fassl, M., Gröber, L. T., & Krombholz, K. (2021, May). Stop the consent theater. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-7).

principles.³⁰³¹³² It is appropriate to also refer to these as 'surveillance advertising' or 'tracking-based advertising' due to the extremely privacy invasive manner in which these enable advertising companies and data brokers to track the individual and make unknown assertions about their personal lives – primarily under the guise of showing relevant advertising. There has been sufficient research showing this problem exists, is wide-spread, and is against both the spirit and the wording of the GDPR and other laws³³ and recent case law finding some aspects to be illegal³⁴, including a CJEU decision.³⁵ Yet there have been no concrete legal measures to reign in these practices – presumably because of the strong ties between advertising and economic interests.

At the same time, there have been no prominent technical solutions to support either the controllers or the data subjects in addressing the problem. Notable actors are Consent Management Platforms (CMPs) who are vendors providing solutions for controllers to meet GDPR consent obligations, and thus intended as processors, implement the IAB's TCF and RTB mechanisms while also introducing additional non-compliance of their own.³⁶ Enforcement against these has not been proportionate in response, with some enforcers taking an exorbitantly long time to make a decision³⁷ even when there are 'low hanging fruits' on clear violations that could have improved the GDPR's consent problems.³⁸ While the recent procedural addition to the GDPR addresses this by introducing specific timelines,³⁹ the effects and benefits from this are yet to materialise.

Another set of relevant actors are the browser, device, and OS vendors as these form the bulk of the 'consumer-side' or 'user-side' technical interfaces. Despite 'cookie consent' and 'cookie popups' being a prominent and widespread nuisance, no browser vendor or their affiliated organisations and standardisation bodies have proposed or introduced a solution to address this. Instead, all popups repeat an agnotologist statement that the user can control cookies through their browsers or devices – whereas the only controls provided to the users are to see (how many) cookies exist for a given website's address and to delete them. There has been no intent or motivation to develop, for example, a setting or interface for websites

³⁰ Matte, C., Bielova, N., & Santos, C. (2020, May). Do cookie banners respect my choice?: Measuring legal compliance of banners from iab europe's transparency and consent framework. In 2020 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP) (pp. 791-809). IEEE.

³¹ Gray, C. M., Santos, C., Bielova, N., Toth, M., & Clifford, D. (2021, May). Dark patterns and the legal requirements of consent banners: An interaction criticism perspective. In Proceedings of the 2021 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems (pp. 1-18).

³² Santos, C., Bielova, N., & Matte, C. (2020). Are cookie banners indeed compliant with the law? deciphering EU legal requirements on consent and technical means to verify compliance of cookie banners. *Technology and Regulation* pp. 91–135 (2020).

³³ Veale, M., & Borgesius, F. Z. (2022). Adtech and real-time bidding under European data protection law. *German Law Journal*, 23(2), 226-256.

³⁴ Veale, M., Nouwens, M., & Santos, C. (2022). Impossible asks: can the transparency and consent framework ever authorise real-time bidding after the Belgian DPA decision?. *Technology and Regulation*, 2022, 12-22.

³⁵ C-604/22 IAB Europe v Gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit (2024)

³⁶ id 23-27

³⁷ The Irish Data Protection Commission opened a statutory inquiry into Quantcast International Limited on 02nd May 2019 but has yet to publish a decision nearly 7 years since then.

³⁸ The findings from the Test-driven approach towards GDPR compliance (2019) provided a list of granular consent requirements and their implementation in Quantcast CMPs to the DPC

³⁹ Regulation (EU) 2025/2518 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 November 2025 laying down additional procedural rules on the enforcement of Regulation (EU) 2016/679

to declare *the category* of cookies being used or to provide users with more granular controls that would allow them to actually implement what the CMPs and websites tell them is possible. This is an important observation as the data subject's perception of the problem is shaped by such statements and interfaces, especially when narratives are framed to blame the laws instead of the implementers. These actions by CMPs also result in them becoming controllers under the GDPR due to their determination of processing.⁴⁰ This means websites (as controllers) who utilise CMPs are utilising tools that help them violate the GDPR instead of providing them compliant solutions. This is difficult to challenge because the GDPR does not contain provisions to address the power imbalance between processors who exert this behaviour on controllers, and instead requires enforcement via a case-by-case basis which is both costly and time-consuming. The principle of the market self-correcting itself has not materialised here as we know of no cases where a controller has taken a processor to court for providing products that increased their GDPR liability.

Eventually, browser vendors have taken a stance and action – to delete or remove the popup entirely⁴¹, and even gone so far as to propose automating "accept all" in consent dialogues when it is the only option.⁴² These represent what can be considered as US-centric perspectives on privacy, which are at odds with EU norms as well as fundamental rights. The US-centric approach is adversarial and assumes that 'bad actors' will always work to violate norms and it's up to the 'good actors' to stop them. This results in approaches that seem user-friendly, such as removing the popups by any means possible, but also go against the very fundamentals of consent and data protection which are essential to self-determination. More importantly, it normalises the popups existing and their associated problems, which is akin to treating the symptoms rather than the underlying disease. Legally, it also creates problems as the popups in theory are also fulfilling obligations on provision of information and the rights to object and withdraw consent, which means that browsers interrupting this process can have legal effects for both the controller as well as the data subject.

Apple, notably, has implemented its own solution in the form of 'App Tracking Transparency' (ATT), which is a OS-level switch that must be turned on to prohibit apps from asking the user if they can track them.⁴³ It works by asking developers to self-declare they are performing tracking when submitting their apps to the App Store, and then using this metadata to control whether the unique "advertising identifier" generated by Apple and associated with the user is shared by the OS with the app. In this, 'tracking' is vaguely defined and enforced as apps still embed tracking scripts outside of ATT's control⁴⁴, and where clear legal violations happen despite the privacy-friendly perception of Apple

⁴⁰ Santos, C., Nouwens, M., Toth, M., Bielova, N., & Roca, V. (2021, May). Consent management platforms under the gdpr: processors and/or controllers?. In Annual Privacy Forum (pp. 47-69). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

⁴¹ Brave (2022) Blocking annoying and privacy-harming cookie consent banners <https://brave.com/privacy-updates/21-blocking-cookie-notices/> and Mozilla (2025) Block cookie banners on Firefox <https://support.mozilla.org/en-US/kb/cookie-banner-reduction>

⁴² Mozilla (2022) Firefox Cookie Banner Handling <https://community.mozilla.org/en/campaigns/firefox-cookie-banner-handling/>

⁴³ Apple (2021) If an app asks to track your activity <https://support.apple.com/en-us/102420>

⁴⁴ Kollnig, K., Shuba, A., Van Kleek, M., Binns, R., & Shadbolt, N. (2022, June). Goodbye tracking? Impact of iOS app tracking transparency and privacy labels. In Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (pp. 508-520).

products.⁴⁵ Apple's implementations also depict a typically US-centric problem, where instead of working to implement things in a way that aligns with regulations (in particular GDPR), and allow their users to express their legal rights associated with consent and legitimate interest, it has opted to implement its own private regulation in the form of ATT. This creates ad-hoc challenges as regulators must now reinterpret ATT's implementation, align it with legal mechanisms, and then find ways to exercise enforcement.

The third set of actors are the advertising companies, which include prominent Big Tech platforms like Google who have their own browser and ecosystem, Meta (formerly Facebook), and Amazon. These are significant violators of privacy norms, but are difficult to reign in due to their large presence and dominant positions, as well as the difficulty in bringing up enforcement under laws that do not address. These challenges have led to the Digital Services Act (DSA) and Digital Markets Act (DMA) which contain specific provisions to tackle this. In particular, Google's use of Android OS and Chrome web browsers as dominant platforms exerts significant pressure on the ability of other actors to implement solutions. An example of this is the limitation of third-party cookies which other browsers have implemented as a privacy-preserving measure, but where Google's positions have resulted in investigations by the UK Competition and Market Authority (CMA) due to its dominant positioning in both browser and advertising markets simultaneously.⁴⁶ As a result, Google has opted to continue its advertising operations over the privacy of its users. Another example is IAB's TCF, which is a technical specification to enable websites to communicate consent and other decisions from the user's terminal device to the website (via the CMP), and also to enable the use of RTB. A notable absence from TCF implementations is the ability to communicate a withdrawal of consent – which means that TCF enables 1000s (literally) of companies to receive personal data and carry out surveillance advertising, but it will not let the same companies know that the user has withdrawn or objected. This lapse is despite the apparent claims made by IAB regarding the TCF respecting the GDPR, and is still present after several years and versions of iterative development. This problem is also important as the TCF (and RTB) are fully website controlled, and in reality CMP-controlled. Data subjects, as users, have no ability to control this, and the only technical innovations developed so far to address it are third-party browser extensions that work by automating the process of refusing or objecting via provided controls in the interface.⁴⁷

Finally, solutions in the form of automated technical signals, such as Platform for Privacy Preferences (P3P)⁴⁸ and Do not Track (DNT)⁴⁹ have been developed to the point where they reached advanced stages of standardisation in W3C and were adopted by a portion of the

⁴⁵ Kollnig, K., Shuba, A., Binns, R., Van Kleek, M., & Shadbolt, N. (2022). Are iPhones Really Better for Privacy? A Comparative Study of iOS and Android Apps. *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*.

⁴⁶ Investigation into Google's 'Privacy Sandbox' browser changes: The Competition and Markets Authority (CMA) investigated Google's proposals to remove third-party cookies (TPCs) on Chrome and replace TPCs functionality with a range of 'Privacy Sandbox' tools. <https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/investigation-into-googles-privacy-sandbox-browser-changes>

⁴⁷ Nouwens, M., Bagge, R., Kristensen, J. B., & Klokmose, C. N. (2022, April). Consent-o-Matic: Automatically answering consent pop-ups using adversarial interoperability. In *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems Extended Abstracts* (pp. 1-7).

⁴⁸ W3C (2006) Platform for Privacy Preferences 1.1 <https://www.w3.org/TR/P3P11/> Retired 2018

⁴⁹ W3C (2019) Tracking Preference Expression (DNT) <https://www.w3.org/TR/tracking-dnt/>

market. Instead of further developing these, due to market pressure and the stated reason of DNT itself causing privacy issues as websites were not respecting it and instead using it for increased profiling.⁵⁰ The specific narrative of privacy signals increasing "fingerprinting" continues to be used as a deterrent for any complexity in the signal, as these form additional data elements which increases the amount of data available to uniquely identify and track the user across websites. Due to the prevalence and widespread acceptance of this reason, any proposal for consent and privacy management is doomed to be accused of increasing privacy risks and is thus likely to face hurdles in acceptance and adoption.

It is worthwhile to note that Apple removed DNT from its Safari browsers in 2019⁵¹, and then introduced ATT in 2021 as a way to restrict tracking, despite the possibility of reintroducing DNT. This also shows that approaches that have been developed to significant maturity and were discarded are considered as 'failures' and are not adopted. In addition, compared with ATT, the specification for DNT shows greater maturity, clarity, and practicality as it was accompanied by a compliance and scope document⁵² that described, amongst others, requirements for compliance across first and third parties, prohibitions on use of the signal for further purposes such as personalisation, following the principles of data minimisation, and an explicit list of permitted purposes such as security ('legitimate purposes' in GDPR terms). ATT is an Apple-exclusive creation which does not have any formal specification nor adoption outside Apple's permitted cases in its own ecosystem. In the interim, other platforms like Google and Microsoft, which were involved in earlier signal efforts, have not come up with any alternatives for signals.

Google's efforts, mentioned in the earlier para, were instead focused on their 'Privacy Sandbox', which despite many name changes, was abandoned due to conflicts with their position as a dominant browser and multiple dominant positions in the advertising ecosystem.⁵³ This approach involved Google's Chrome browser deciding how the user's activities translated to advertising targeting, and where the user's identity would be hidden from advertisers while Google would be in control of matching the user's activities to advertising bids. These kind of approaches, typically pitched as "privacy preserving", have also been proposed by others browsers like Firefox⁵⁴ and have been adopted by Apple across its browser and platforms.⁵⁵ This also represents a fundamental shift in technological providers dictating how online privacy functions by developing approaches that facilitate advertising goals over user interests and privacy preservation. Even though many developed features do not make it into the final version, such as in the case of Firefox, or have been forced to be abandoned, such as for Google – the fact that the only approaches taken by these actors are ones that do not enable individuals to exercise self-determination. This is an important observation as this is contrary to how consent should function, and also relates to the US-centricity of technical providers who prefer to not enable consent and instead work on being in control of the privacy management or to facilitate objections and opt-outs.

⁵⁰ Hill, K. (2019, February 6). Apple Is Removing 'Do Not Track' From Safari. Gizmodo. <https://gizmodo.com/apple-is-removing-do-not-track-from-safari-1832400768>

⁵¹ id

⁵² W3C (2019) Tracking Compliance and Scope <https://www.w3.org/TR/tracking-compliance/>

⁵³ id 40

⁵⁴ Privacy-Preserving Attribution (2025) – experimental feature that was eventually removed <https://support.mozilla.org/en-US/kb/privacy-preserving-attribution>

⁵⁵ Apple Advertising & Privacy <https://www.apple.com/ie/legal/privacy/data/en/apple-advertising/>

A good example of this is the Global Privacy Control (GPC), which is currently undergoing standardisation at the W3C.⁵⁶ GPC is a signal that has only one possible value – 'active', which indicates that the user "requests their data not be sold to or shared with any party other than the one the person intends to interact with, or to have their data used for cross-context ad targeting". The specification's recent additions (February 2026) further clarify the terms by link to the W3C's Privacy Principles,⁵⁷ and state "the person is at least requesting that there be only one data controller and that the data not be used for ad targeting in another context, even if that context is owned by the same business". The GPC is the most mature and well-adopted privacy signal so far⁵⁸ with many prominent service providers supporting it as well as browsers such as Firefox, Brave, and DuckDuckGo implementing it. In the W3C's standardisation progression scale, it is closer to becoming a formal standard. The GPC was developed based on the language and requirements of California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA)⁵⁹ in 2020, and was discussed as being relevant to the GDPR's Article 21(5) objections for legitimate interest when proposed to the W3C.⁶⁰ This followed from GDPR's text itself allowing for automated exercise of the right to object, with the GPC being its technical implementation. Over time, the specification added specific text that expanded its potential role under the GDPR by noting automated withdrawal of consent, which is not mentioned in the GDPR text but also not prohibited by it.

However, due to the inherent differences in language, the role of GPC under EU law is unclear and indeterminate.⁶¹ Broadly, the GPC is a signal that communicates the data subject's wishes that they do not want their personal data to be: 1) Shared with a third party, and 2) Used for cross-context advertising. Aligning this with GDPR is different because of the differences in what is meant by 'third party' and 'controller' in GDPR as compared to the GPC specification (which links to the Privacy Principles for definitions). Though the GPC's use of controller aligns with that in GDPR as the determinant of means and processing, the real-world's complexities involve multiple actors often playing roles of joint-controllers, as seen in the FashionID CJEU case law.⁶² The GPC specification also introduces a qualifier about the controller the data subject "intends to interact with", which is a subjective concept and needs a case-by-case determination. Pessimistically, it is likely that every advertising company will claim the user intended to interact with their ads and use this as a loophole, much like Facebook's justification that its users entered into a contract to see ads on the platform rather than use the social media service it is primarily known for.⁶³

Even if the GPC authors (and editors) intend for each jurisdiction's authorities and courts to determine what should be the interpretation and enforcement of the GPC for their own laws, the role of standards (whether legally recognised or defacto) requires taking into account

⁵⁶ W3C (2026) Global Privacy Control (GPC) <https://www.w3.org/TR/gpc/>

⁵⁷ id 22

⁵⁸ Hausladen, K., Wang, O., Eng, S., Wang, J., Wijaya, F., May, M., & Zimmeck, S. (2025). Websites' global privacy control compliance at scale and over time. In 34th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 25) (pp. 5837-5856).

⁵⁹ California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) (2018) www.oag.ca.gov/privacy/ccpa

⁶⁰ W3C (2020) Privacy CG Teleconference, 10 December
<https://github.com/privacycg/meetings/blob/main/2020/telcons/12-10-minutes.md>

⁶¹ Zimmeck, S., Pandit, H. J., Borgesius, F. Z., Santos, C. T., Kollnig, K., & Berjon, R. (2025). Can the GPC standard eliminate consent banners in the EU?. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2512.08856*.

⁶² Case C-40/17 Fashion ID GmbH & Co.KG v Verbraucherzentrale NRW eV. (2019)

⁶³ NOYB (2019) Facebook: We don't need your consent!
<https://noyb.eu/en/facebook-we-dont-need-your-consent>

their existing language and restricting interpretations to what is effectively aligned with it. This means that even if GPC were standardised and adopted tomorrow, and even if the GDPR authorities produced guidance clarifying what is the exact interpretation of the signal in terms of consent and legitimate interests, this would not be sufficient. Actors with vested interests are highly likely to intentionally either not implement it in the prescribed manner or to contest the enforcement via legal procedures that can stretch up to 5 years or more. Further, the GPC's specification only describes the mechanism for the signal and its fixed meaning. It does not dictate how the user controls the signal for a specific website as this is considered an implementation detail for each browser or device maker to subjectively interpret. In theory, this is another opportunity for actors with vested interests, such as CMPs, to introduce new dark patterns and forms of malcompliance.⁶⁴

The GPC signal is legally enforceable in California and several other states due to the laws either directly mentioning use of automated signals like GPC or by providing the authorities with the power to determine this. In contrast, the GDPR mentions technical signals for automated objections to legitimate interest, but does not state how to determine which signals must be legally implemented and respected. This means even if GPC is standardised, actors in the EU are likely to simply declare they will not support it nor respect it, or create interpretations and implementations which deviate from the GPC specification. In addition, the use of signals also raises questions regarding conflicts, with research showing the existence of multiple privacy signals communicating contradictory privacy choices.⁶⁵ Finally, the GPC is a new specification still being developed, and whose interpretation and enforcement is still thus evolving. While it is simpler than DNT to implement and apply, the state of its documentation and the normative guidance and clarity provided is quite lesser than what was available for the DNT. As a result, it needs significant additional effort to consolidate this understanding and conceptualise a common understanding to ensure its uniform application by stakeholders.

All of these serve to highlight that despite the problems with consent and online privacy being known, the typical actors that comprise the 'market' have neither shown the intent nor the will to resolve the problem in a way that aligns with the intended EU norms and values.

Analysis of Article 88b

Box 4 The proposed Article 88b requires critical clarification on three important aspects:

1. Paragraphs (1) and (6) mention the use of technical means to automate decisions regarding giving and refusing consent, as well as the right to object to legitimate interest. However, the right to withdraw consent pursuant to Article 7(3) is missing and should be included as being necessary to support in an automated manner.
2. The requirements for consent under the GDPR require an explicit action by the data subject⁶⁶ which is at odds with giving consent in an automated manner. Article 88b therefore must introduce a new requirement for validity of giving consent

⁶⁴ id. 24, 26, 34

⁶⁵ Hils, M., Woods, D. W., & Böhme, R. (2021). Conflicting privacy preference signals in the wild. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.14286*.

⁶⁶ Recital 32 GDPR states "Consent should be given by a clear affirmative act..."

through automated means that is aligned with existing requirements of freely given, specific, and unambiguous indication as per Article 4(11).

3. Where the GDPR requires explicit consent, such as for processing of special categories of personal data,⁶⁷ Article 88b should clarify that the automated means of expressing such consent should meet the higher set of requirements for validity regarding the data subject explicitly expressing their consent.

Box 5 To ensure the (harmonised) standard sufficiently covers the necessary implementation details, Article 88b should cover the following:

1. Machine-readable information representing the consent request by a controller in order for the data subject's terminal device can make use of this information in order to determine the automated decision to be expressed as per Paragraph (1). This includes a consistent format for the controller to declare that it supports the automated mechanism and to provide accurate and interoperable information necessary to request valid consent (e.g. the purpose, recipients).
2. Mechanism through which the data subject's terminal device can determine whether a controller (i.e. website, service) supports the intended automated expression of consent or rights, and if so then how the data subject's decision or expression of rights should be communicated to the controller.
3. Mechanism for expression of the data subject's withdrawal of consent or objection to legitimate interest when the data subject is not currently visiting the website or service, and the corresponding mechanism by the controller to receive and implement this.
4. Mechanism for the controller to communicate confirmation of the data subject's expressed decision
5. Mechanism for the controller to communicate their rejection of the data subject's objection under Article 21(5) and the compelling legitimate grounds used to justify this decision.
6. Mechanism for the controller and the data subject to maintain a record of the expressed decision and interaction in a manner that supports the principle of accountability in Article 5(2).
7. Mechanism through which the data subject can revise their prior decision upon subsequent visits, and for the controller to recognise this change and implement it.
8. Requirements to ensure the automated decision making does not impact the data subject's rights or freedoms and is used in a manner that is limited to only supporting the data subject is automating the expression of their decisions.

The Omnibus proposal for the GDPR introduces Article 88b with the objective of "for automated and machine-readable indications of individual choices and respect of those indications by website providers once standards are available."⁶⁸ In the accompanying staff working document,⁶⁹ the EU Commission provides further context and rationale for the

⁶⁷ Article 9(2)(a) GDPR

⁶⁸ id 1 pg.21

⁶⁹ COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Accompanying the documents Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL Amending Regulations

proposal, which includes notes on 'single-click' controls for users to both give and refuse consent as well as to exercise their right to object to legitimate interest,⁷⁰ and that this is to be implemented through a (harmonised) standard that provides the necessary details.⁷¹

Paragraph (1) of Article 88b introduces an obligation on controllers to ensure their interfaces used to request and manage consent also allow data subjects to (a) give consent and (b) refuse consent as well as exercise the right to object regarding legitimate interests – through automated means and in a way that meets the requirements for consent. The presumed intent of this obligation is to have the user's device or browser manage the consent dialogue and popup shown in an automated manner without requiring the user to take actions.

Paragraph (4) states that the (harmonised) standard mentioned in (1) will be initiated through a request made by the Commission to one of the European Standards Development Organisations (SDO), which are likely to be CEN and ETSI. The objective of the standard's request is mentioned as "for the interpretation of machine-readable indications of data subjects' choices". This means that the Commission will draft a request for the standard based strictly on the final text of the regulation, and the standards development bodies in turn will also consider the scope to be strictly what has been requested. It is vital to therefore ensure that this paragraph is sufficiently detailed on what the standard should be. The current phrasing has several aspects missing regarding necessary implementation details based on the descriptions earlier in this document (see Box 1 and 2) regarding how consent and online privacy can be understood as a technical process, and the differing perspective of users in managing their consent and privacy through it.

Points 1 and 2 in Box 5 are necessary to ensure there is a standardised way for the controller to communicate their request for consent in a machine-readable form, and in a manner that the data subject's terminal can correctly interpret and use to make a decision. This can take the form of embedded information in the webpage or a separate url providing the information. Prior EU-funded research justifies the technical feasibility for this requirement.⁷² Without this standardised mechanism, controllers or groups may produce proprietary forms of consent requests that limit the ability of the data subject's terminal device to determine if the request is valid and to take appropriate decisions. Providing required information in this case means all the information that is required by the GDPR for the consent request to be considered valid. Having this information allows the data subject's terminal device to determine, first if the request is complete i.e. is all necessary information provided – if not the request is invalid, and second it allows the data subject to automate with more flexibility. For example, if the data subject wants to refuse all consent requests where their email is involved or where there are too many recipients – they can do so by

(EU) 2016/679, (EU) 2018/1724, (EU) 2018/1725, (EU) 2023/2854 and Directives 2002/58/EC, (EU) 2022/2555 and (EU) 2022/2557 as regards the simplification of the digital legislative framework, and repealing Regulations (EU) 2018/1807, (EU) 2019/1150, (EU) 2022/868, and Directive (EU) 2019/1024 (Digital Omnibus) Amending Regulations (EU) 2024/1689 and (EU) 2018/1139 as regards the simplification of the implementation of harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Digital Omnibus on AI) {COM(2025) 837 final} - {COM(2025) 836 final}

⁷⁰ id Section 1.3.2.2

⁷¹ id Section 1.3.2.3

⁷² *D2 Final Technical Deliverable*. (n.d.). Privacy-as-Expected: Consent Gateway funded with funding under the NGI_Trust program which was part of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 825618. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5086239>

configuring their terminal device based on the availability of personal data category in the consent request as per the standard.

Point 3 in Box 5 addresses the assumption implied by Article 88b that the automated mechanism will operate only when the data subject is using the website or the service. Even though 'online interface' does not necessarily mean the data subject must be present on it, it is better to make this explicit to avoid ambiguity. This will avoid data subjects having to necessarily revisit the same website or service in order to change their decision – which may be burdensome. Instead, it is better to technically automate the process so that if the data subject is withdrawing their consent or objecting to legitimate interests, they can do so without visiting the website e.g. by having their browser send the request directly to the online interface provided by the controller. Point 7 follows from this to enable the controller to understand a changed decision expressed by the data subject in an automated manner.

Point 4 in Box 5 is a necessity to avoid malpractices or introducing new forms of non-compliance. If the data subject's terminal device sends a signal representing their decision, but there is no response back from the controller, it leaves a dangerous ambiguity as to whether the signal has been correctly communicated and whether the controller intends to respect it. The response also provides a way to test whether the controller is indeed accepting receipt of the decisions, and whether this is then subsequently reflected in their technical aspects involved in processing such as collection of data via network requests or the loading of specific scripts on a webpage. Point 5 follows from this as the GDPR allows controllers to refuse to respect an expressed objection to legitimate interests but only if they have compelling legal grounds. It is vital for data subjects to understand that their objection has not been successful and why, and to do so in a manner that is integrated with the automated approach.

Point 6 in Box 5 ensures that the standard allows the creation of records for the decision and the interaction conducted between the data subject and the controller. While this is already an obligation under the GDPR for controllers,⁷³ this ensures that data subjects can also keep their own records. The feasibility of this approach is justified through the availability of the ISO/IEC TS 27560:2023⁷⁴ standard, which is freely accessible, for consent records as well as their provision to data subjects as 'consent receipts' to establish trust and accountability through shared record-keeping. Existing research-backed work also shows the alignment of this standard with GDPR requirements, and the existence of machine-readable vocabularies that can be used to create interoperable consent records.⁷⁵

The introduction of an automated mechanism that expresses decisions on behalf of the data subject can be classified as automated decision making in the meaning of the term used in Article 22. This warrants that technologies developed to implement the intended automated processes should be done in a manner that ensures the data subject does not suffer as a result of using them, or that they do not become a vector for increasing the risks to the data

⁷³ Article 7(1) GDPR

⁷⁴ ISO/IEC TS 27560:2023 Privacy technologies — Consent record information structure
<https://www.iso.org/standard/80392.html>

⁷⁵ Pandit, H. J., Lindquist, J., & Krog, G. P. (2024, August). Implementing ISO/IEC TS 27560: 2023 consent records and receipts for GDPR and DGA. In *Annual Privacy Forum* (pp. 228-251). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

subject or their rights. For example, consider the case where current CMPs also provided the automated mechanisms for both the data subjects and the controllers, and continued to use dark patterns or aspects which are contrary to the data subject's expectations – such as communicating 'accept' even if the configured preferences should have resulted in a 'reject'. In such cases, the use of automation would actually be of detriment to the data subject. To ensure this does not take place, the standard must also establish obligations, controls, and guidance to ensure a procedural aspect of impact assessments that ensure the data subject's rights and freedoms are not impacted negatively.

Paragraph (4) continues on the role of standards by stating that "Online interfaces of controllers which are in conformity with harmonised standards ... shall be presumed to be in conformity with the requirements covered by those standards ..." This is typical phrasing used to justify the role of standards in meeting requirements of the law. Of importance here is that the phrasing also allows controllers to self-determine conformity (from "presumed to be") which is at odds with the trend of non-compliance implementations discussed earlier in the document. There is a real and significant risk that controllers, or CMPs, or specific providers, may claim that their implementations are in conformity, or that the non-conformant aspects are due to a misunderstanding, and other similar avoision tactics. To prevent this, the alternative is to empower a body to determine conformity, and who will then be responsible for ensuring foreseeable malpractices do not take place before any mechanism is widely deployed.

The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) is the logical choice for this role as it is comprised of all Member State GDPR Supervisory Authorities (or, as DPAs), has the remit to undertake investigative and prescriptive activities as part of its duties in producing normative guidance as well as ensuring consistency in decisions, and also would provide a pan-EU outcome that avoids fragmentation and gold plating. This approach is aligned with similar measures taken by the German federal law (TDDG)⁷⁶ where services must first be audited to be confirmed with the list of requirements and are then 'approved' for deployment as consent managers.⁷⁷ Currently, it lists one service – consent.eu⁷⁸ – as being approved, which is sufficient to state that the approach is feasible. A similar approach also exists in India's Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP)⁷⁹ which introduces the concept of 'consent manager' and a process for its approval based on demonstrated conformity.⁸⁰

Paragraph (6) creates an obligation for web browser providers that are not SMEs to ensure their browsers provide the technical means described in the Article. Here, the term SME under EU law involves organisations that have less than 250 employees (staff headcount),

⁷⁶ BMDV (2024) Regulation pursuant to Section 26(2) of the TDDG and amending the Special Fee Regulation Telecommunications

⁷⁷ Services for consent management according to § 26 TDDG

<https://www.bfdi.bund.de/DE/Fachthemen/Inhalte/Telefon-Internet/Einwilligungsverwaltung/Einwilligungsverwaltung.html>

⁷⁸ <https://www.consent.eu/>

⁷⁹ Digital Personal Data Protection Rules 2025

<https://www.meity.gov.in/documents/act-and-policies/digital-personal-data-protection-rules-2025-gDOxUjMtQWa>

⁸⁰ Article 4 DPDP

and a turnover of ≤€50 million or a balance sheet of ≤€43 million.⁸¹ The rationale of excluding SMEs from obligations typically refers to their limited resources or capacity, and thus the need to support them through relaxed legal obligations. In this case, the exception for SMEs cannot be justified based on size or revenue alone as this may end up with cases where a dominant web browser is exempt because it is an SME. It would be better to have a criteria that is aligned with the impact on data subjects, such as number of users being utilised in implementing the DSA. It is also important to note that controllers that are SMEs are not exempt from the obligation to provide the technical aspects in their online interfaces per Paragraph (1), and that therefore browsers should also not be exempt. Compared to controllers, who may or may not have the technical knowledge or capacity, providers of web browsers are in a highly capable position to implement technical aspects of the standard. By using number of users as a criteria, the intended benefit to hobby or niche browsers can still be achieved without potential loopholes or edge cases that will need additional legislation.

Can automatically given consent still be valid consent?

Box 6 Article 88(b) (1)(a) requires automated means for the data subject to give consent to the controller. However, the automatic expression of given consent may be at odds with the requirement for unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes. A definition for validity of automatically given consent is thus necessary to ensure the automation meets existing requirements, and also to ensure it does not create wider risks such as automatically granting consent to all requests regardless of sensitivity or number of recipients. A working definition of acceptable automation is to use the existing notion of 'purpose compatibility' where the data subject first determines the (broad) processing they want to permit through their consent with sufficient detail (e.g. purposes, operations, whether to share with recipients), and then to automatically communicate given consent only when the controller's request for consent is compatible. To avoid malpractices and ensure consistency in this approach, the standardisation should also include developing a controlled vocabulary of purposes with details of processing, personal data categories, whether recipients are necessary, and so on that can be used by controllers to request consent and by data subjects to automate their decisions.

The GDPR's requirement for valid consent⁸² consists of four criterias: (1) freely given – which requires data subjects to have meaningful choice and control to make the decision; (2) specific – which means the consent should be for specific purposes and processing; (3) informed – which requires the data subject to have sufficient information to make an informed decision; and (4) unambiguous indication of wishes – which requires a clear, deliberate, and affirmative act from the data subject that confirms they are giving their consent. Of these, (1) concerns the situation in which the controller decides to ask for the data subject's consent, and requires assessment of power imbalance, coercion, and other forms of manipulation to ensure the data subject was 'free' to give their consent. (2) and (3) concern specific information associated with consent and which can be determined based on the notice or request provided for consent. For implementation of Article 88b, the information

⁸¹ EU Commission – SME definition

https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/smes/sme-fundamentals/sme-definition_en

⁸² id 17

involved in communication of request from controller to data subject in a machine-readable form must satisfy the specific and informed conditions. (4) effectively requires the data subject to take an action when giving consent. In this, it is important to first clarify that the GDPR only requires the affirmative action by the data subject when they want to give their consent. Such an affirmative action is not strictly necessary when refusing consent or withdrawing. The rationale for this is evident when considering the role of given consent as a legal basis – which means that the data subject must have taken an action to enable it. Since refusing and withdrawing consent do not lead to any processing of personal data nor can they be used as legal basis, there is no need for the data subject to take additional effort nor for the controller to require it. From these arguments, it should be clear that the refusing and withdrawal of consent through automated means is compatible with the existing GDPR.

However, there are key issues when considering giving consent through automated means. First, what does 'automated' mean? The concept of automation is a broad spectrum, where one end involves the data subject (manually) making a decision to give consent and the automation merely referring to this decision being communicated through technical means, and where the other end requires no effort by the data subject while some mechanism automates making the decision and giving consent on behalf of the user. It is necessary to walk through this spectrum to understand the practical challenges of implementing Article 88b, and through this process, identify concrete restrictions for 'automation'.

Automation category 1: The data subject manually makes a decision concerning a specific purpose for a specific controller, and their web browser automates its expression on a website. An example of this is the data subject indicating in their browser's configuration dashboard that they want to accept the purpose "Improve the performance of the website by sharing device information to better understand user variations" for the controller "European Commission", and when the user visits the Commission's website, their browser communicates that the data subject has given this consent to the controller. This case is compatible with the GDPR's notion of unambiguous indication as the data subject has taken a clear and affirmative action, and the only difference is when this decision is made and when it is communicated to the controller. However, this is undesirable as it requires manual effort on the part of the data subject which defeats the purpose of automation.

Automation category 2: The data subject makes a broad decision for a single purpose but not for a specific controller, and the web browser automates its expression on any website that requests consent for this purpose. An example of this is the data subject deciding they are okay with the purpose "Improve performance of the website through analytics" and indicating this in their browser settings. When the browser next visits the Commission's website who requests consent for this purpose, the browser automatically communicates that the data subject has given their consent. In this, the key issue is whether the data subject has unambiguously indicated their consent to the Commission as they only took an affirmative action to decide on the purpose but not a specific controller.

On the one hand, the 'category' of purposes can be consistent across websites, such as many websites using analytics to improve performance. In this sense, the processing is the same, and the data subject's action can be deemed sufficient evidence of having assented to this. On the other hand, each controller's processing, even if for the same purpose, can be considered a distinct kind of processing due to the differences in actors and

implementations, and thus the data subject's action may not be sufficient to consider their consent as an unambiguous indication. The resolution of this kind of automation thus resides in how the 'compatibility of purposes' is defined between the data subject's initial decision, which is likely to be broad to benefit from automation, and the controller's requested purpose, which must be specific to meet GDPR requirements.

Describing how to assess compatibility between two purposes is necessary, but not described here in depth. A simple heuristic is to assess the purpose (e.g. website improvement), operations over data (e.g. collect, store, use, share), categories of personal data (e.g. device identifiers), and recipients (e.g. controller, third parties) along with the intended benefits (e.g. to controller, to data subject). This ensures that the data subject's actions do not lead to unwanted aggressive granting of consent. For example, if the data subject specifies they are okay with "Website performance improvements" as the purpose, and website A is automatically granted consent for this and proceeds to collect and use the device identifier to analyse patterns and make improvements. This is desirable and probably what the data subject intended. But website B also uses the same purpose description and is granted consent, but then collects much more identifiable data and also shares it with a large number of third parties.

This shows that the data subject's automation of giving consent requires a risk and impact assessment component that prevents them from accidentally making broad decisions. One way to implement this is to check the data subject's configured decision to give consent in their browser and ensure it is not problematic. Another option is to standardise the purposes along with other components (processing, personal data, recipients, etc.) and to strictly only give consent for these. Even if standardisation is desirable, and explicitly mentioned in Article 88b, the approach of flagging risky decisions made by data subjects should also be included in the standardisation to ensure the technical providers of consent management solutions for data subjects support them in upholding their rights, and also as a way to prevent mischief in manipulating the data subjects into giving broad and expansive consent.

Of particular note, the implementation by consentor.eu involves showing a brief popup to the data subject when giving consent is automated with the rationale that this provides data subjects with an opportunity to change their decision. Even if this is a useful design choice, the fact that the data subject's inaction leads to granting of consent still requires clarification – in particular regarding whether the prior configuration made by the data subject in their settings can be a sufficient indication of their decision.

Automation category 3: The data subject makes a broad decision on what processing is not acceptable to them, and the browser automatically expresses that the data subject has given consent to all other activities. An example of this is the data subject deciding that they do not want to give consent to the purpose "Personalised tracking-based advertising" and configuring this in their browser. When they visit the Commission's website, it requests consent for the purpose "Improve performance of the website through analytics" and the browser automatically expresses that the data subject has given consent. In this case, even though the data subject had taken a specific action, that action was not to indicate that they agree with the purpose requested by the website. Such automation is therefore unlikely to meet the bar for unambiguous indication of consent under the GDPR. That being clarified,

such configurations are still desirable and helpful for the user to automatically refuse consent, which does not require satisfying the unambiguous indication condition.

Automation category 4: The data subject does not configure any specific decision, and an algorithm determines whether to accept or refuse a consent request. An example of this is a machine learning model that analyses past decisions taken by the data subject and automatically determines whether the next request should be accepted or rejected. Another example is using an LLM to parse a consent request and deciding whether to accept or refuse it. In both cases, the data subject has taken no affirmative action, and therefore this is also unlikely to satisfy the unambiguous indication condition for valid consent.

Defining automation of giving consent: Based on the possibilities of automation, a working definition can be formulated based on 'compatibility with data subject's accepted purposes' for how automated giving consent can be accommodated in the GDPR's existing elements for valid consent. The requirement for automated giving of consent to be 'compatible' means that in order for the web browser to automatically give consent in response to a website's request, it is essential for the given consent to be compatible with the decision made by the data subject through their browser settings to grant such consent. In turn, the data subject's configuration must be sufficiently detailed such that its automated expression in response to a controller's request can result in valid consent as per the GDPR.

These conditions are necessary to prevent potential tactics such as browsers, apps, or even websites using and respecting the privacy signal, but then creating new forms of dark patterns or coercions in the interface used to configure the privacy signal. These requirements can also be understood as a mere expansion of the requirement for valid consent, which has already been established in the GDPR, to the entire process of making the decision by including the configuration of the privacy signal as a step in the consent decision-making process. However, by separately expressing these requirements, the added benefit is that withdrawal, refusal, and objections also benefit from their application.

How to define a 'valid decision' made using a privacy signal?

Box 7 The proposed Article 88b only refers to privacy signals in the abstract and does not dictate their validity. In order to ensure the signals are developed and implemented in a manner that avoids known tactics regarding dark patterns, manipulations, coercions, and other forms of malicious practices, it is necessary to create a framework for their validity. This is necessary to prevent potential tactics such as browsers, apps, or even websites using and respecting the privacy signal, but then creating new forms of dark patterns or coercions in the interface used to configure the privacy signal.

To implement this without introducing new concepts, we can reuse the conditions for valid consent and expand them to be conditions for valid decisions. This has the added advantage of reusing established case law in the GDPR regarding the interpretation of these concepts. To do so, we consider the privacy signals must satisfy the conditions of being **freely given, specific, informed, and an unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes**. Further, these concepts must be applied to the entire process which

includes the configuration of the privacy signal as well as its use, whether done explicitly or implicitly. By utilising these concepts beyond valid given consent, we also benefit from their use in other actions – withdrawal, refusal, and objections – using the signal. This is without prejudice to giving **explicit consent** or giving consent to **high-risk** activities, where the data subject **MUST** be asked for confirmation.

In addition to these, existing settings or configurations that do not satisfy one or more of these conditions, which may also be in the form of signals, should still be considered as valid and binding where they are not capable of giving consent or permitting processing. An example of this is the GPC signal which is already being used in browsers. Since such technologies and signals are already valid, it would be beneficial to **enforce them immediately** while the privacy signal that aligns with the above requirements is being developed, deployed, or validated. This generic and broad condition also allows other devices and digital environments to benefit from having settings or configurations that express the decisions of the data subject without risk of additional unwanted processing.

Privacy signals must themselves satisfy requirements for being a freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indications of the data subject's wishes: The privacy signal is an 'agent' that acts on behalf of the user. While the earlier discussions discussed this role in context of the relationship between the 'agent' and the website or controller, the validity of consent must also be assessed based on the relationship between the privacy signal's implementation and the data subject. This is critically necessary because the privacy signals would be implemented by an entity other than the data subject, and therefore could introduce additional problems and deceptive or manipulative concerns that deteriorate the quality and validity of the consent for the data subject. Rather than introducing new qualitative criteria for privacy signals, it would be appropriate to reuse the existing criteria for valid consent and extend them as criteria for 'valid decisions expressed by a privacy signal'.

Though the GDPR does not require such criteria (i.e. freely given, specific, and so on) for objecting to legitimate interests, we consider them essential as part of indicating the data subject's wishes regardless of whether this is for giving consent or exercising their right to object. To do so, we adapt the requirements for valid consent from the EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent, and apply them to the context of privacy signals.

The condition of '**freely given**' must mean that the decision expressed through the privacy signal satisfies the requirements of: 1) **imbalance of power**: where the configuration and use of a privacy signal does not preclude the data subjects from having a real choice and control over their decision; 2) **conditionality**: where the use of the privacy signal or its configuration does not create a compulsion on the data subject, or be disguised as part of other settings or configurations; 3) **granularity**: the use of a privacy signal must not induce decisions that result in excessive processing of personal data or create a situation where the data subject has to accept additional processing greater than what they wanted to express; and 4) **detriment**: the data subject must not suffer detriment arising from the use of the privacy signal or from the configuration of the privacy signal in a specific manner.

The condition of '**specific**' consent means that the consent is given in relation to one of more specific purposes and that the data subject has a choice in relation to each of them. While the 'choice' aspect also relates to the earlier requirement of granularity, the preceding condition of being able to agree to specific purposes is an important requirement as it avoids overtly broad and expansive consent requests. For privacy signals, this translates to the ability for the signal to both be configured regarding and in communicating the data subject's given consent in terms of the specific purposes. Since each given instance of consent must also individually be capable of being withdrawn, and similarly refused, it can also be inferred that the requirement for specificity applies to privacy signals in relation to these actions. Without this, a privacy signal may be capable of giving consent for a specific purpose, but not to refuse it or withdraw it for that purpose. This is *imbalanced* for both the controller as well as the data subject. Even if the GDPR does not require withdrawal or refusal or objecting to legitimate interests to follow the same requirements of specificity, and that data subjects may find utility in having a broad signal that widely refuses, withdraws, or objects, this is an additional capability without prejudice to having granular control over each individual purpose.

Further, since the GDPR also considers the individuality of purposes based on the data involved, the broader goal or objective, the intended benefits, and the involvement of specific recipients, the privacy signal must also be capable of differentiating purposes based on these criteria. Broadly, this means the privacy signal must not only be capable of expressing choices regarding different purposes for the same controller (or website), but also for distinct controllers and websites (including third parties). When implementing, the privacy signal must therefore be possible to be configured and applied or exercised for each controller and website the data subject visits. **Signals that allow communicating given consent but do not allow such specificity cannot be considered valid.**

Signals without specificity that do not communicate giving consent, but allow communicating refusal, withdrawal, or objection, do not violate these requirements, but are unlikely to be acceptable to controllers due to the imbalance in the ability of the data subject to permit and to prohibit the processing by using the signal. At the same time, certain settings or configurations on the terminal device or other contextual factors may already sufficiently communicate the intent or wishes of the data subject to *not permit* or *to prohibit* certain processing. Such wishes must still be considered as applicable and respected.

The requirement to be **informed** is essential for consent as the data subject must know what they are deciding about in relation to the processing of their personal data. Per the EDPB guidelines, the requirements for informed consent are: 1) controller's identity; 2) purpose of each processing operation; 3) categories of personal data being processed; 4) applicable right to withdraw consent; 5) the existence of automated decision making; and 6) potential risks involved due to transfers. When a privacy signal is used to communicate the decision to give consent, it is essential for the data subject to have been informed using these information elements. However, the necessity to be informed can also become a *barrier* to the use of automation, and could backfire, for example by introducing popups or notices to ensure the information is provided. Instead, the privacy signal must be capable of *automatically ensuring* this information is available and in an accessible form so that the data subject can inspect, *if required*, whether before, during, or after making their decision to give consent.

Realistically, this allows for a broad range of possible signals: one extreme is where the privacy signal uses pre-configured or standardised purposes that meet information elements 2–6 and only ensures and records element 1 (controller identity) **before expressing given consent**. The other extreme is where the privacy signal must first confirm each and every element before communicating given consent because each website or controller may have a different combination of purpose, data, etc. In the first instance, the signal is simple, and data subjects can benefit from a reduced choice, but also lose a high-degree of self-determination. In the second example, the data subjects may have greater choice and therefore benefit from a high-level of self-determination, but can also be overburdened with excessive choices and settings. A sensible middle ground is to not allow a single entity to standardise the manner in which purposes and these information elements are defined, and to then allow the data subject's privacy signal implementation to use them in a manner that benefits the data subject without burdening them. Good examples of how such elements can be standardised in a machine-readable form are available in the EN ISO/IEC 29184:2020 standard on privacy notices and its aligned 'sister standard' ISO/IEC TS 27560:2023 which provides a machine-readable record of actions. Note: 27560:2023 is currently being revised to be applied for all legal bases, and would thus also be capable of recording objections to legitimate interest. The benefit of reusing these is that 27560:2023 defines the use of a privacy receipt, which is an acknowledgement of a decision or event provided to the data subject. This means the privacy signals can record each interaction, in a manner that assures the information elements required for being informed are present, and can also record the decision being communicated, in a standardised manner, and with the possibility of an explicit confirmation from the controller.

The last requirement is the **unambiguous indication of wishes** which requires that the data subject have a clear and affirmative action to indicate they have given their consent. When using automated privacy signals, it is not possible for the data subject to give such actions as this would defeat the purpose of automation and create excessive disruptions. At the same time, by not having the data subject be able to exercise their will for any individual decision, the principle of consent itself would be in question. Therefore, the privacy signal must ensure two things: 1) It should require that the communication of given consent include an *unambiguous indication* that the data subject wishes to do so; and 2) the data subject's configuration or decision to use the privacy signal in this manner must also constitute an *unambiguous indication*. The first is necessary to meet the requirements for valid consent, and the second is necessary to ensure that the data subject did indeed wish to give their consent – and is thus an expansion of the requirement to the stage where the data subject configures the privacy signal to do so.

What constitutes an unambiguous indication is subjective, but in most cases this refers to the use of a button or similar UI element that is clicked by the data subject to exhibit an affirmative action. While necessary for given consent, this is not necessary for refusing or withdrawing consent, or objecting to legitimate interests. Therefore, the privacy signal can utilise a confirmation from the data subject, without excessive intrusive UX like popups, that the data subject does indeed want to give their consent as configured for the privacy signal. This can be similar to existing non-intrusive UX used in browsers, such as when using the microphone or camera during meetings. At the same time, data subjects may not want to be faced with these different kind of 'popups', and may want to not receive them and give signal

automatically. This should be allowed, **but only for cases that are low-risk** to the data subject. For high-risk cases, especially where special categories are involved, or where there are excessive data categories or a high number of recipients, it would be desirable to flag this to the data subject before confirming and communicating their consent. This is inline with the existing principles of GDPR, such as in the exception to Article 30 records and the Article 35 obligation to conduct an impact assessment. Further, it is not possible to automate 'explicit consent', such as that required in Article 9 prohibitions, which also necessitates the privacy signal to have such a mechanism. In this, we also note that the requirements for *explicit consent* regarding unambiguous wishes are higher than those for *expressed consent*. Thus, the privacy signal must also be capable of recognising which level of expression and confirmation is necessary, and to be able to obtain this from the data subject where necessary. From the data subject's perspective, such settings already exist, and are familiar mechanisms in their smartphones and browsers, for example when sharing location the choices given are 'always allow', 'allow while using', and 'allow once'.

List of existing standards for building the privacy signal

1. For expression of information, the **Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)**⁸³ provides a taxonomy of purposes, personal data categories, etc. in a machine-readable manner. This is useful to represent the consent request from the controller in a way that can be used by the data subject's software. If it is decided that granularity is not needed and the standard itself provides a list of purposes and their machine-readable expression, then the DPV will not be needed. However, it is still suggested to use this as a starting block in discussions as the DPV has been built over 8 years, **is an outcome of multiple past and ongoing Horizon projects**, and has a significant amount of coverage in terms of concepts to represent necessary information. It also has **implementations supporting ISO standards on privacy notices and consent records, with published specifications on implementing them for the GDPR**. The DPV has also been used in the technical specifications for Health Data Spaces (called HealthDCAT-AP) which were funded by the Horizon program for implementation of EHDS, and the AI portal specifications (called MLDCAT-AP) which were funded by SEMIC under the Commission's Interoperable Europe programs.
2. The **Advanced Data Protection Control (ADPC)**⁸⁴ is a specification developed by NOYB and WU to express decisions in a machine-readable form. It provides the technical means for the controller website and the data subject's browser or terminal device to communicate which purposes are involved, whether the data subject is accepting, refusing, or withdrawing them, and also to object to use of legitimate interests. However, it is not sufficiently detailed to dictate how this should work in a consistent and interoperable manner, and thus requires work. It has also not been developed further since its inception. As with the DPV, it is better to utilise existing efforts and improve them as needed as starting from scratch would also risk introducing new complexities and deviations.

⁸³ <https://w3id.org/dpv>

⁸⁴ <https://www.dataprotectioncontrol.org/spec/>

3. **EN ISO/IEC 29184:2020⁸⁵** privacy notices – considerations for how requests for consent should be made in a technical manner (note this is EN which means it has been approved for use in the EU).
4. **ISO/IEC 27560:2023⁸⁶** consent records – information to include in a request and how to maintain records for a consent decision or interaction. **It is freely available.**
5. **ISO/IEC 27701:2025⁸⁷** on PIMS (Privacy Information Management System) – controls and governance for implementation of technical systems.
6. **ISO/IEC 27556:2022⁸⁸** on the privacy preference manager.
7. **IEEE 7012:2025⁸⁹** – Though this standard does not relate to consent or legitimate interests, it involves a protocol for machine-readable expression of preferences and decisions which are of relevance here as they can be used as the standardised set of purposes or configurations for the use of privacy signals. **It is freely available.**

Changelog

- Fixes to typos, grammatical errors, and phrasing without any change in meaning.
- In List of existing standards for implementing privacy signals: Corrected the indication of ISO/IEC TS 27560:2023 as freely available instead of EN ISO/IEC 29184:2020

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<sup>85</sup> <https://www.iso.org/standard/70331.html>

<sup>86</sup> <https://www.iso.org/standard/80392.html>

<sup>87</sup> <https://www.iso.org/standard/85819.html>

<sup>88</sup> <https://www.iso.org/standard/71674.html>

<sup>89</sup> <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7012/7192/>